

Factors Affecting the Job Performance of the Personnel of Holy Spirit Police Station, Quezon City

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Abstract:- Job performance is the measure of how effectively an individual completes their job duties and contributes to their organization's goals. This study aims to identify the factors affecting the job performance of personnel at the Holy Spirit Police Station. Specifically, it examines personal and professional factors, work-related matters, and environment-related factors. Additionally, the study analyzes if there is a significant difference in how these factors influence job performance, and from the findings, proposes a framework that can contribute to the body of knowledge in this field. This study used quantitative method through descriptive research design, through purposive sampling, one hundred thirty-eight personnel of Holy Spirit Police Station located at St. Joseph, St. Corner, San Simon, St, Brgy Holy Spirit, Quezon City were chosen as respondents. Results showed that officers' effectiveness at work is greatly impacted by their overall well-being. Issues such as discrimination, inconvenient work areas, poor ventilation, and inadequate equipment are identified as challenges in doing duties. Further, problems include a lack of support from the community, agencies, and barangay, as well as inadequate help from private groups. However, study shows that there is no significant difference on the assessment of respondents in terms of the three mentioned components. With the end view the research proposes a framework to further enhance the job performance of PNP personnel .

Keywords:- Environment-Related Matter, Job Performance, Personal Factors, Professional Factors, Work-Related Matter.

I. INTRODUCTION

Performance in every workplace is viewed as an individual's performance of their assigned tasks. Performing their tasks in the workplace is affected by factors such as physical and emotional stress. Stressors also lead to some health condition which contributes to poor performance (Powell & Hawes, 2020). Hence, Santiwong (2017) argues that the effective performance of police is essential in the fulfillment of organizational goals. Setting a good framework may lead to successful and increased productivity of the police personnel. Further, Aboazoum et al., 2015 emphasized the criticality of the job of police and pointed out several aspects that influence the standard of police performance when they are doing their tasks in law enforcement.

In addition, job performance can also be explained as the way of police in achieving their what was prescribed in their job descriptions and their actions in their workplace (Jex and Britt 2014). It was supported by the study of Tembur (2017) emphasizing that job performance is an assessment of police that delivers to an organization. Service on the other hand is activities that are done in an organization which give importance to its productivity. However, an unhealthy and distressful work environment of the police officer can impair their performance including their health, both physical and emotional. In general, all these issues contribute to the police officer's poor overall performance. Likewise, it was lamented by Picincu, (2019), that excessive noise and other distractions have an impact on mental attention and productivity. Accidents and injuries can also occur in a dangerous workplace. These are only a handful of the aspects that influence the workplace. And according to Cottini & Ghinetti (2012), essence of working environment to the police performance stating that if the workplace does not attract police officers and they have a negative perception of various workplace environment elements such as absenteeism, performance, stress-related illness, and not being productive, and it affects their duties and obligation as a police officer as a result it affects the organizational growth and its productivity

However, when the organizational environment is friendly, safe, and trusted, it will have a positive impact on the police officer that leads to creativity, productivity, commitment, which also influences the police organization satisfactorily (Bhatti, 2018). Crandall and Eshleman (2003) emphasize how personal and environmental factors shape individuals' expressions of prejudice, pointing to upbringing and societal norms as significant influences. Additionally, Thompson and Cavender (2020) stress the importance of collaboration between law enforcement agencies and communities for effective policing, highlighting the teamwork involved in community-oriented policing efforts. Moreover, Tetric and Peiró (2012) discuss how work-related and environmental factors affect employee well-being and performance, focusing on job demands and organizational support. Together, these studies suggest that while people may differ, certain universal factors like societal norms, teamwork in policing, and support from organizations can impact job performance assessments across different people. This highlights how personal, professional, and environmental factors all play a role in shaping how individuals perceive and evaluate job performance.

Republic Act No. 6975 (December 13, 1990) established the Philippine National Police (PNP) under a reorganized Department of the Interior and Local Government. Republic Act No. 8551 (February 25, 1998) amended certain provisions of R.A 6975 and provided for the reform and reorganization of the PNP. (Philippine National Police Operational Procedures.)

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Job performance among police personnel is influenced by a variety of factors, including personal, professional, work-related, and environmental elements. Studies have consistently shown that psychological well-being plays a crucial role in officers' performance. For example, Violanti et al. (2017) found that stress and trauma negatively impact police job effectiveness, leading to burnout and lower productivity. Similarly, Jaramillo et al. (2005) highlighted the importance of emotional intelligence, with officers demonstrating higher emotional resilience performing better in high-pressure situations.

Organizational factors, such as leadership style and institutional support, are also critical. Agarwal (2009) emphasized that positive organizational culture and clear communication improve job satisfaction and performance. However, De Guzman (2012) noted that Philippine police officers often face resource shortages and inadequate training, which hinder job effectiveness.

Work-related factors, including workload, working conditions, and resource availability, significantly impact performance. Research by Tucker et al. (2003) and Cooper (2000) found that poor work environments and excessive workload contribute to fatigue and lower productivity. In the context of local police stations in the Philippines, Javier et al. (2016) pointed out that inadequate facilities and equipment can be particularly problematic for performance.

Additionally, community relations and external support play a role. Skogan (2006) found that positive community-police relationships enhance officer effectiveness, whereas Rogers et al. (2013) observed that low public support leads to decreased morale. However, studies focusing on how local government support and community collaboration affect police performance in Philippine settings are limited.

Despite existing research, significant gaps remain in understanding how these factors interact in local Philippine police stations, particularly at the barangay level. The current study aims to address these gaps by examining the specific factors affecting job performance at the Holy Spirit Police Station in Quezon City, providing insights into the local challenges and offering recommendations for improvement.

➤ *Conceptual Framework*

The researcher presents figure 1 as the conceptual framework of the study which guides the conduct of this study. The first block is the input is anchored in Republic Act No. 8551, which serves as the legal basis by focusing on enhancing the professionalism and performance of the Philippine National Police (PNP) through improved capabilities and job performance. It utilizes Organizational Behavior Theory to understand how individual and group behaviors within the organization, influenced by motivational factors, job satisfaction, and organizational culture, impact overall job performance and effectiveness. The study follows standard operating procedures (SOPs) to assess the level of agreement on the severity of factors affecting job performance, including personal and professional-related matters, work-related matters, and environmental-related matters. Additionally, it examines the significant differences among these variables based on respondents' perceptions. Data is collected using a Survey Questionnaire, designed to capture the experiences and opinions of mobile patrollers regarding these factors. The analysis involves Descriptive Statistics to summarize and describe the survey data and Inferential Statistics to test hypotheses and determine the significance of differences among variables. This structured approach ensures a thorough examination and understanding of the elements impacting job performance, leading to actionable insights for improving practices at HSPS.

The second block is the process that the researcher had undergone to attain the objective of the study, this involves an informal interview and survey questionnaire that was administered to the respondents. The process begins with developing and distributing a structured Survey Questionnaire to collect quantitative data from mobile patrollers on personal, professional, work-related, and environmental matters affecting their job performance. To complement this, Actual Interviews are conducted, either face-to-face or virtually, to gain qualitative insights into participants' experiences and perspectives. Additionally, Library Research is undertaken to review existing literature, providing context and background relevant to law enforcement job performance. The collected data is then subjected to Data Analysis to identify patterns and correlations, followed by Tabulation and Summary of Data to present key findings in an organized manner using tables and charts. Statistical Analysis is employed to test hypotheses and determine the significance of findings using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Observations within HSPS are made to validate data and gain firsthand insights into working conditions and practices. Finally, the data is Collated to ensure systematic organization, and the results are Interpreted to draw conclusions, make recommendations, and identify areas for improvement in job performance. After the instruments were retrieved it was tallied, tabulated and interpreted for presentation of data and tables.

Fig 1 Research Paradigm of the Study

The third block of my study focuses on the output and benefits of the research findings for various stakeholders. It underscores how the insights gained can be instrumental in shaping and guiding policy formulation. Specifically, the study aims to enhance the implementation of environmental laws and policies, which is crucial for the effective conservation, protection, and development of environmental assets in Quezon City. By providing a comprehensive understanding of the factors affecting job performance among personnel at Holy Spirit Police Station (HSPS), the research offers valuable data that can inform and improve policy-making processes. The actionable recommendations derived from this study will not only help improve working conditions and job satisfaction for the patrollers but also strengthen the enforcement of environmental regulations, ultimately contributing to better environmental management and preservation in the region.

➤ *Significance of the Study*

This part of the study displays the list of people to whom this study will be useful. They are the following.

Police Officers. The research is significant to the police officers of Philippine National Police to allow them to assess themselves on what factor are they going to improve after the research is done so that they can improve and work on it for better performance

PNP Officials. This research study also aimed to give a wider perception and knowledge about the factors that affects the job performance of the Philippine National Police Personnel further to provide recommendation for the PNP Personnel on how to unravel those factors that affects their performance likewise, to mold their performance.

Stakeholders of the PNP. This study may also help the stakeholders of PNP with regards to the factors that affect the job performance of their subordinates. Through this study and references, they will be able to understand or make strategies and techniques in order to help and improve the performance of the PNP officers.

Future Police Officers. They may use this study to have knowledge on how the Police Officers will perform their duties and responsibilities. They may build their ideas and plans in a more progressive manner by considering the needs and wants of the people or the society.

Philippine National Police Organization. Through this study, it may help them to expand and understand more the significance of the performance and its impact to the service and image of the organization.

Community. Community is the one receiving and experiencing the kind of service PNP personnel has been

executing. There should be a harmonious relationship between these two, that is why there is a Police Community Relation. Community must be cooperative with regards to the laws, programs and activities of the law enforcement and these are being implemented for the sake of the safety and security and maintenance of peace and order in the country. Thus, through this study the community helps to improve their level of awareness regarding the factors that affect the job performance of the PNP personnel.

Researcher. The completion of the study can thoroughly help the researcher to understand more topics researched and studied. This study may provide an immense aid to the researcher on his future profession. It will benefit the researchers to have more knowledge regarding the factors that affect the job performance of the PNP Personnel and also to know the techniques and strategies in dealing with those factors.

Future Researcher. This study can help them in conducting their own research. It provides wide opportunities for topics and references that might be useful for researchers to be used on their own. In addition, this study will also encourage them to conduct further. The research topic will inspire them to do more and go beyond that may develop the case being studied.

➤ *Objectives of the Study*

This study aimed to investigate the factors influencing the job performance of personnel at the Holy Spirit Police Station in Quezon City. The specific objectives were:

To identify the personal, professional, work-related, and environmental factors that affect the job performance of police officers at the station.

To assess the impact of these factors on the overall effectiveness and efficiency of the officers in fulfilling their duties.

To analyze whether significant differences exist in the perceived influence of these factors on job performance among officers of different ranks or divisions.

To propose a framework aimed at enhancing the job performance of police personnel, based on the findings of the study.

Through these objectives, the research aimed to contribute to a better understanding of the various factors that shape the performance of law enforcement officers at the local level, with implications for improving operational efficiency and personnel well-being within Philippine police station.

III. METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the procedure and methodology being used by the researchers in conducting the study. Several activities in the plan included the following: research design, research locale, research subject, the population of the study,

scope and limitations of the study, ethical considerations, research instrument, data gathering procedures, statistical treatment of the data, and dissemination of the research outcome

➤ *Research Design*

Quantitative research design is a systematic approach to research that focuses on collecting and analyzing numerical data to understand patterns, relationships, and trends. It is often used to quantify variables, assess measurable phenomena, and establish relationships between different factors. Conceptually, quantitative research is based on the idea that social phenomena can be observed and measured objectively, allowing for statistical analysis that leads to generalizable conclusions. This design relies on the collection of data through methods such as surveys, experiments, and existing records, and typically uses statistical tools to interpret the results.

In relation to my study on the factors affecting the job performance of personnel at Holy Spirit Police Station (HSPS), quantitative research design plays a crucial role in achieving reliable and actionable results. The "why" of using a quantitative approach in my study lies in the need for objectivity and precision. Quantitative research provides a way to systematically measure these factors using numerical data, which allows you to compare results across different variables and draw statistically sound conclusions.

The "how" of applying quantitative research design involves the use of structured tools like a survey questionnaire with a Likert scale, which I have chosen for data collection. This tool enables the gathering of quantifiable data from a sample of 138 personnel that have been subjected to statistical analysis.

By employing quantitative research design, it benefits from the ability to analyze relationships between the different factors affecting job performance in a precise, replicable, and generalizable way. The quantitative data generated will allow us to identify patterns that are statistically significant, providing evidence-based insights into the key factors that contribute to performance issues. This helps in forming targeted interventions that are backed by data, leading to improvements in both individual performance and overall organizational efficiency at HSPS.

Moreover, the generalizability of the findings ensures that the insights gained from the study can be applied to broader contexts, potentially influencing decision-making and policy development not only at HSPS but in other law enforcement settings as well. Utilizing quantitative research design, my study achieves a clear, objective understanding of how different factors impact job performance and provides a strong foundation for developing effective solutions.

➤ *Research Method*

This study used quantitative-evaluative method. Quantitative descriptive research was used in this study because it enables the researcher to determine the relationship between variables and to understand the topic.

The Descriptive-Evaluative Method combines the systematic observation and description of a phenomenon with an assessment of its effectiveness or impact. Conceptually, the descriptive component seeks to provide an accurate portrayal of the subject under study, such as behaviors, conditions, and characteristics, without altering them. It relies on gathering detailed data through surveys, observations, and records, which results in a comprehensive understanding of the current state of the phenomenon. On the other hand, the evaluative component focuses on assessing the value, performance, or effectiveness of programs, processes, or practices. It involves analyzing both quantitative and qualitative data to determine if specific goals are being met, often leading to recommendations for improvement.

In relation to my study on factors affecting the job performance of personnel at Holy Spirit Police Station (HSPS), this method is particularly relevant because it comprehensively explores and assesses the different factors influencing performance. The descriptive aspect captures the key variables—such as work conditions, support systems, training, equipment, and personal well-being—by systematically collecting data through a survey questionnaire with a Likert scale. This descriptive data provides a clear snapshot of the current conditions experienced by mobile patrollers, enabling you to understand the different influences on their job performance without any direct intervention.

The evaluative component then allows to assess how these factors impact performance by analyzing the data collected. Through evaluation, can determine which factors have the most significant influence on performance and identify areas where improvements can be made. For instance, if the analysis reveals that inadequate training

significantly affects job performance, this finding provides actionable insights that can lead to recommendations for enhanced training programs or improved systems of support. By combining both descriptive and evaluative elements, your study moves beyond merely documenting the factors affecting performance to providing a critical assessment of current practices and offering suggestions for improvement.

The use of this method in my study is vital because it not only helps you understand the current state of performance among HSPS personnel but also evaluates the effectiveness of existing practices, providing a foundation for evidence-based interventions. This dual approach yields a more comprehensive understanding of the challenges and opportunities faced by mobile patrollers, facilitating better decision-making at HSPS and contributing to improved policing effectiveness in your community.

➤ *Population of the Study*

The respondents of the study covered One Hundred Thirty-Eight (138) personnel of Holy Spirit Police Station were chosen as respondents because they have firsthand knowledge and experience about the topic. The non-probability sampling method, specifically purposive sampling, was used in determining the respondents of this study. According to Etikan et al. (2016), when a researcher uses purposive sampling in their study, they choose respondents suitable for their research. The respondents are selected deliberately based on the qualities they have. The researcher finds those qualities in people and gathers their willingness to share their knowledge and experiences. Additionally, the selected respondents are often proficient and well-informed about the study.

Table 1 Respondents of the study and its figure

Respondents	Frequency
Holy Spirit Police Station Personnel	138

➤ *Data Gathering Tools*

A survey questionnaire was the primary data gathering instrument used in the study, formulated based on the specific problems of the study. It was structured by the researcher based on the various literature, theories, informal interviews, and suggestions of the adviser to substantiate the contents of the questionnaire. The researcher adopted a four-point Likert scale type of questionnaire. The tool was composed of questions that sought to answer and draw conclusions from the respondents' assessment.

The survey instrument has undergone a process to test its validity. The questionnaire was structured and submitted to the instructor for further assessment and evaluation. This was subjected to content validation by the assigned experts in the research field of patrol. Hence, an experienced high ranking PNP officer was assigned to validate the format and content of the survey instruments. Their suggestions were considered as the instruments were revised to incorporate their significant ideas. The revised tools will be submitted again for perusal to find possible flaws. The survey instrument was divided into three parts covering personal and

professional matters, work related matters and environmental matters. Hence it also included some preliminary robo-foto questions pertaining to the respondents.

Further the survey instrument has undergone pre-testing and reliability test to further ensure its validity to a respondent who are not really part of the survey revealing a result of Cronbach's Alpha showing (.937) and (.963) which are all higher than 0.3 threshold and above 0.7 implying that all questions are acceptable with good internal consistency.

➤ *Data Gathering Procedures*

The draft survey questionnaire was presented to the researcher's adviser and panel members for comments and suggestions. The researcher sought the approval of the Dean of the graduate school upon validation of the instrument for the interview. After the Dean granted permission, the researcher approached the participants through face-to-face surveys.

Before distributing the survey questionnaire, the researcher explained the nature of the study to the

respondents. Moreover, the mechanics and concepts of answering the survey questionnaire were presented to the selected respondents. The participants voluntarily gave their full consent to be the subject of the study. The data was gathered using a survey questionnaire on a checklist.

Once the survey questionnaire was accomplished, the researcher retrieved, tallied, analyzed, and interpreted the results accordingly. The data gathered will be treated with confidentiality and anonymity maintained not expose the collected data and identity of the participant during and after the conduct of the study.

➤ *Treatment of Data*

To aid the analysis and interpretation of the gathered data in determining the level of Factors Affecting the Job Performance of Patrol Unit. The researcher interpreted and analyzed the data based on the respondent's answers to the questionnaire. For a more valid and meaningful interpretation of the data, the researcher used the 4-point Likert scale, F-test ANOVA, frequency, and percentage to describe the treated data.

➤ *Ethical Considerations*

In conducting this study, ethical considerations were paramount to safeguard the rights and well-being of the participants. Prior to their involvement, the researcher took measures to adequately inform all potential respondents about the nature, purpose, and potential outcomes of the study. Informed consent was obtained, ensuring that participants willingly and voluntarily agreed to take part.

To preserve the confidentiality and privacy of the respondents, their identities were kept anonymous throughout the research process. Any information that could potentially reveal their identities was carefully handled and stored securely. Access to all collected data was restricted solely to the researcher, and participants were assured that their data would be used exclusively for educational purposes related to the study.

No form of incentives or compensation was offered to the participants, emphasizing the voluntary nature of their involvement and preventing any undue influence on their decision to participate. Furthermore, explicit measures were

taken to exclude certain vulnerable groups, such as minors, persons with disabilities, and other sectors, ensuring that the study adhered to ethical standards and minimized any potential risks to vulnerable populations.

The ethical considerations undertaken in this study align with established principles to uphold the integrity of the research process, protect the rights of the participants, and contribute responsibly to the body of knowledge in the field.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this chapter, we present and analyze the findings from this research, offering insights into the data collected and its implications for the research questions posed. The results section provides a detailed account of the quantitative data obtained, including statistical analyses and key findings. Following this, the discussion interprets these results, relating them to existing literature, theoretical frameworks, and the broader context of the study. This dual approach not only elucidates the data but also contextualizes it within the larger scope of the research objectives. By integrating results with discussion, this chapter aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the study's outcomes and their significance.

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets data pertinent to the study. It discussed the level of agreement on the severity of factors that affect the job performance of the personnel of HSPS in the delivery of their services. Analysis and interpretation of data were acquired through the application of descriptive statistics such as: Weighted mean to determine the assessment of the Personal and Professional-related matters; Work-related Matters; Environmental-related Matters; and One-Way Analysis of Variance (F-test) was also used to determine the significant differences of assessment among the respondents towards the three sub-indicators/factors.

➤ *Factors that affect the job Performance of the Personnel of HSPS in the Delivery of their Services*

This section presents the answers for the factors that affect the job performance of the personnel of HSPS in the delivery of their services in terms of Personal and Professional Factors support system.

Table 2 Factors that affect the job performance of the personnel of HSPS in the delivery of their services

Personal and Professional Related matters	WM	INTERPRETATION
1. Family problems affect the performance of duties of police officer	2.97	Agree
2. Relationship issues affect the way a police officer performs his duty	2.94	Agree
3. Lack of professional development may affect successful performance of police officer's duty/responsibilities	3.14	Agree
4. Physical health of the police officer affects his effective performance of duties	3.32	Strongly Agree
5. Mental health issues of the police affect the performance of duties and responsibilities of police officer	3.35	Strongly Agree
6. Financial inadequacy of police officer affects his performance of duty	2.97	Agree
7. Lack of trainings attended by the police affects the performance of police duties	3.22	Agree
8. Course/baccalaureate degree may affect the patrol and field duties of police	2.85	Agree
9. Socialization aspect can affect the performance of police.	3.01	Agree
10. Behavior and attitude of the police can affect in performing police duties	3.31	Strongly Agree
OVERALL	3.11	Agree

It can be seen in the table that the overall weighted mean (WM) of 3.11, interpreted as "Agree," indicates that both personal and professional factors significantly impact the job performance of personnel in the Holy Spirit Police Station (HSPS). Based on 138 respondents, this study implied that these elements collectively have a significant influence on how successful and efficient police officers are.

Results showed that officers' effectiveness at work is greatly impacted by several personal and professional aspects. Overall well-being of a police officer has a significant impact on the effectiveness of doing the duties. A positive work environment and organizational support promotes a sense of commitment and belonging by encouraging teamwork, reducing stress, and enhancing job satisfaction. Chances for career advancement and continuous education provide officers with the skills and information they require, boosting their self-assurance and productivity at work. Also, the negative factors like family or relationship problems greatly affect the performance of a police officers.

The findings suggested that all police officers should be aware of the importance of maintaining their well-being, as well as acknowledging personal struggles including family concerns. Officers can improve their ability to concentrate on their work by giving priority to initiatives which solve these issues. Recognizing the significance of financial stability further emphasizes how important it is to reduce the financial burden so that officers can commit themselves entirely to their work. Investing in continuous training and improving hiring requirements to evaluate essential qualities like communication abilities are necessary in improving performance.

The studies by Ahmad et al. (2018) and Chen et al. (2022) discuss how job stress affects employee performance. Ahmad et al. show how stress can affect police officers' ability to do their jobs well, while Chen et al. highlight how stress can lead to burnout and dissatisfaction, ultimately hurting performance. Song et al. (2020) add that psychological distress makes this connection even more complicated. Together, these studies emphasize the need to address stress and mental well-being to improve how employees perform at work.

Moreover, the physical health, mental health, and the behavior of police officers are seen to be impactful in the performance of their duties. The acknowledgement of the impact of physical and mental health shows that staff members recognize the substantial impact an officer's physical health has on their capacity to carry out their tasks. This emphasizes how important it is to put policies into place that support and preserve officers' physical well-being. Providing resources for stress management, regular health check-ups, and fitness programs can all help to keep officers resilient and physically strong, which will improve their ability to meet the demands of their jobs.

Further, data shows a significant level of agreement on the conduct and attitude of police officers indicates the role that personal characteristics play in determining work

performance. It shows that police officers recognize the value of professionalism, upbeat attitudes, and moral behavior in building public trust and upholding efficient policing procedures.

This suggested that maintaining the physical health of police personnel and maintaining a positive, professional work environment are essential for the police force. The recognition of the relationship between physical health and job performance highlights the necessity of policies and programs that support officers' physical well-being. Examples of such programs and policies include stress management tools, routine physical examinations, and fitness initiatives. Meanwhile, acknowledging the significance of behavior and mindset also means that nurturing a professional and moral culture inside the force is required. By giving priority to these areas, the HSPS can provide its officers with the tools and attitude they need to carry out their responsibilities efficiently, which will improve community relations and service delivery in the long run. When these conditions are met, an officer's concentration, commitment, and morale can all be improved, which raises output and increases job satisfaction of police officers.

In alignment with this, Riebe et al. (2018) highlights the significance of physical fitness in police work, defining it as the ability to perform daily tasks without excessive tiredness and with enough energy for leisure activities. Given the varied nature of police duties, from administrative work to physically demanding tasks like pursuits and arrests, assessing physical fitness is integral to recruitment and training. Supporting this, Queirós et al. (2020) demonstrate the stressfulness of police work, negatively impacting officers' performance, public interactions, and overall health. Given the prevalence of mental health issues like depression, anxiety, and burnout among officers, regular assessment of stress levels is crucial for improving occupational health. Additionally, Blumberg et al. (2019) emphasize the diverse skill set required for effective policing, encompassing physical, mental, emotional, and interpersonal abilities. Despite the prevalence of routine tasks, training for worst-case scenarios remains essential in preparing officers for their roles.

One of the respondents said that the value of police officers' physical well-being, emphasizing its role in guaranteeing their capacity to function efficiently while on duty. It was mentioned that being in good physical condition is necessary to handle work obligations and respond quickly and nimbly to potentially difficult situations (Personal Communication, June 04, 2024).

In addition, the data also showed that Workplace culture, leadership efficacy, organizational support, and training and professional development opportunities are important factors. Knowledge, self-assurance, and job satisfaction may all be increased with the help of a supportive workplace and good training. Performance is also impacted by personal concerns, such as family and relationship challenges, emphasizing the necessity of instilling professionalism in every police personnel. Financial stability

is also essential for preserving concentration and productivity.

Supporting this, Viegas et al. (2023) highlighted how police officers often carry work-related stress home, negatively impacting their family relationships. Their study focused on the connection between quality of life and marital satisfaction among female police officers' spouses. Additionally, the necessity for officers to engage with individuals from diverse backgrounds underscores the importance of social and cultural awareness. Research suggests that officers with college education possess enhanced problem-solving and open-mindedness skills, making them better equipped for community policing initiatives (Fritsvold, 2023). Stressors from work can hamper officers' effectiveness, leading to marital strain and reduced family involvement. Work-family conflict is positively associated with various work and health outcomes among

officers, including shift work, lack of support, and marital issues (Violanti et al., 2017).

A respondent stated that a police officer's performance may be affected by personal troubles since they may bring these issues into their profession. This comment emphasizes how important it is to deal with personal issues so that officers can function at their best when on duty. It stresses how important it is to give officers access to support services in order to assist them deal with and get past personal challenges (Personal Communication, June 04, 2024).

➤ *Factors that affect the Job Performance of the Personnel of HSPS in the Delivery of their Services.*

This section presents the answers for the factors that affect the job performance of the personnel of HSPS in the delivery of their services in terms of Work-Related Matters.

Table 3 Factors that affect the Job Performance of the Personnel of HSPS in the Delivery of their Services

SUB-INDICATORS	WM	INTERPRETATION
1. Discordant relationship of police officers to his/her workmate affects his/her performance.	3.17	Agree
2. Inconvenient working area affects the mood and performance of the PNP personnel.	3.14	Agree
3. Lack of flexibility in scheduling the workload and safety in the workplace.	3.14	Agree
4. Lack of support from superior might lead low confidence among the members of the PNP personnel.	3.20	Agree
5. Discrimination among members the police organization greatly contribute to their performance.	3.21	Agree
6. Poor remuneration leads to dissatisfaction of police personnel in the delivery of their services.	3.12	Agree
7. Not granting annual leave to a PNP personnel leads to physical and emotional exhaustion.	3.20	Agree
8. Not granting annual leave to a PNP personnel leads to physical and emotional exhaustion.	2.78	Agree
9. Lack of incentives is one of the factors that drive a police officer to receive bribes.	3.07	Agree
10. Non-existing of provision for physical and mental health benefits makes police demoralize.	3.27	Strongly Agree
11. Poor communication equipment and devices leads to the delay of the PNP personnel in responding calls.	3.14	Agree
12. Poor communication equipment and devices leads to the delay of the PNP personnel in responding calls.	3.20	Agree
13. Poor ventilated facilities greatly affect the performance of the PNP personnel during office work.	3.30	Strongly Agree
14. Unsuitable equipment and work tools in work hinder the performance of PNP personnel.	3.27	Strongly Agree
15. Non-availability or lack of vehicles which results to difficulty to respond for a call.	3.26	Strongly Agree
OVERALL	3.16	Agree

The table showed that the general weighted mean is 3.16 with the interpretation of agreement indicating that work related matters affect the job performance of the personnel of HSPS in the delivery of their services. Issues such as discordant relationships, discrimination, inconvenient work areas, poor ventilation, and inadequate equipment are identified as key challenges impairing productivity and morale. Moreover, the lack of support from superiors, poor remuneration, inflexible scheduling, and unsafe working conditions promotes stress and dissatisfaction. Inadequate leave policies, lack of incentives, subpar communication equipment, vehicle shortages, and absence of comprehensive health benefits further impede efficiency and morale.

This implied that there is a considerable impact of work-related elements on police officers' efficacy and efficiency

when doing their tasks. These results highlight how important it is to handle work-related issues to maximize police effectiveness and guarantee efficient service delivery. Addressing these concerns through improved working conditions, better support and remuneration, proper leave policies, and incentives, alongside provision of health benefits, holds the potential to substantially enhance morale and performance within the Holy Spirit Police Station.

Ensuring better performance among police officers requires the organization to fulfill the needs of every personnel member. By meeting these needs, the organization can enhance satisfaction levels among officers, promote a greater sense of commitment to serving the community. This involves providing adequate resources, such as training, equipment, and support services, to enable officers to perform

their duties effectively. Additionally, addressing issues related to compensation, work-life balance, and career advancement can further contribute to officer satisfaction and motivation.

Supporting these findings, Ghasemy et al. (2021) emphasized the impact of supervisory support and involvement on job satisfaction, influenced by interpersonal conflict and emotional states. Similarly, Tillman et al. (2018) highlighted how mistreatment by supervisors can diminish employees' sense of hope and commitment, ultimately affecting their performance. Additionally, Burke (2019) pointed out that while taking time off during holidays can provide immediate relief from stress, it is often temporary, with stress levels resurging upon return to work. Thus, consistent breaks throughout the year are essential for achieving the cumulative health benefits associated with annual leave.

The findings from Table 2 highlight significant challenges within the police force. These include the absence of provisions for physical and mental health benefits, poorly ventilated facilities, inadequate equipment, and a shortage of vehicles. These issues not only affect the quality of service provided by the police but also jeopardize the safety of both officers and the public.

It implied that if these problems are not addressed comprehensively, they could lead to a decline in officer morale, decreased trust in the police among the public, and increased safety risks for everyone involved. Hence, it is important to invest in improving resources, facilities, and support for officers. By doing so, officers can enhance their ability to perform duties effectively, ensure their safety, and create a sense of security within the community.

In corroboration to these findings, Demou et al. (2020) outlined leadership, organizational change, culture, workload, and working hours as primary sources of stress for police officers, along with experiences of PTSD, anxiety, and depression. Similarly, Baron et al. (2021) underscored the need to enhance coping skills for workplace stress but highlighted a research gap in identifying specific stressors. They advocated for addressing these stressors systematically to develop more effective interventions and foster healthier work environments. Moreover, Tengpongsthorn (2017) highlighted the importance of work effectiveness for organizational success. Effective policies aimed at enhancing employee productivity led to favorable returns on investment and sustainable growth, while a lack of support and processes results in ineffectiveness and disengagement among individuals, hindering performance expectations.

According to one respondent, PNP personnel's performance is affected by having the wrong gear and tools for the job. When officers don't have the right equipment, it

makes their work harder. Making sure they have what they need is crucial for them to do their jobs well and stay safe. So, it's important to address these equipment problems to help PNP personnel do their best (Personal Communication, June 4, 2024).

The table's data provides important insights into factors that might lead police officers to accept bribes. The low score of 2.78 for not allowing PNP personnel to take annual leave indicates that this issue is seen as less significant compared to others, but it still suggests that a lack of rest can cause dissatisfaction and burnout, potentially affecting job performance and ethical decisions. Meanwhile, the higher score of 3.07 for lack of incentives shows a stronger agreement that insufficient rewards or pay make officers feel undervalued, which can push them toward corrupt actions.

This implied that dealing with these problems could result in significant advancements for the police department. Strengthening incentive programs to offer better rewards and compensation, together with reviewing leave regulations to guarantee officers receive enough rest, can greatly increase job satisfaction and lower the risk of corruption. These adjustments would promote a more morale and efficient police force in addition to raising officer morale. Thus, a safer and more balanced society would result from increased public trust and confidence in law enforcement.

Supporting these points, Tenney et al. (2023) highlight how incentives and rewards boost employee motivation and overall workforce morale. Meanwhile, Devi and Fryer (2020) propose a balanced approach to police incentives to prevent abuse while maintaining accountability. Despite concerns raised by McAdams (2016) about potential negative outcomes, Harris (2023) suggests the importance of designing incentives that promote ethical behavior. Additionally, Siegrist's (1996) effort-reward imbalance model emphasizes the impact of rewards, including vacation time, on employee health, stressing the need for balance between effort and compensation.

According to one respondent, annual leave and incentives contribute to a healthier mindset, enabling them to perform their duties effectively. Police officers need rest to maintain their well-being. Regular breaks are essential for sustaining their overall health and job performance. Adequate rest and rewards ensure they can handle their responsibilities efficiently and ethically (Personal Communication, June 4, 2024).

➤ *Factors that affect the Job Performance of the Personnel of HSPS in the Delivery of their Services?*

This section presents the answers for the factors that affect the job performance of the personnel of HSPS in the delivery of their services in terms of Environmental Related Matters

Table 4 Factors that affect the Job Performance of the Personnel of HSPS in the Delivery of their Services

SUB-INDICATORS	WM	INTERPRETATION
1. Lack of support coming from the community makes it difficult for the Appendix 111 PNP personnel to resolve a particular case.	3.31	Strongly Agree
2. Lack of support from other agencies contributes to a much difficult job and poor performance of police.	3.20	Agree
3. Non-participation of Barangay personnel on the police programs and activities produces difficulty in the performance of police duties.	3.21	Agree
4. Lack of assistance from private organizations makes the job of police difficult and poorly perform their duties.	2.95	Agree
5. Lack of assistance from private organizations makes the job of police difficult and poorly perform their duties.	2.96	Agree
OVERALL	3.12	Agree

Table 3 provides insight into the environmental elements influencing how well Holy Spirit Police Station personnels perform at work. With a weighted mean score of 3.12 overall, these sub-indicators have a big impact on police work. Problems include a lack of support from the community, agencies, and barangay, as well as inadequate help from private groups. Building more support and collaboration among sectors is important for addressing these issues.

The results highlight how important it is for law enforcement to interact with the community and collaborate closely with other organizations. Improved community relations can help police win over residents' trust and cooperation, which will be beneficial in both crime prevention and more efficient crime solving. Additionally, collaborating with barangay authorities and other agencies may provide significant resources and assistance, improving the organization and effectiveness of police work.

This suggested that it's essential to concentrate on projects that improve connections and collaboration between different organizations. This entails funding community policing, maintaining constant contact with barangay authorities and other agencies, and establishing partnerships with private groups. Police can perform their duties more effectively and improve community safety and law enforcement confidence by addressing these environmental factors head-on.

In addition to these points, there is consensus on the benefits of coordination and collaboration among agencies and organizations to address complex issues efficiently. This approach ensures improved intelligence sharing, leading to higher-quality data, better problem mapping, enhanced decision-making, and collaborative problem-solving techniques, as highlighted by Gerassi et al. (2017). Moreover, as outlined in the Local Government Code of 1991 and Republic Act No. 7160, the Barangay plays a crucial role in maintaining peace and order at the community level. Professionalizing Barangay Police Security Officers (BPSOs) ensures public safety, peace, and order, as emphasized in DILG Memorandum Circular 2003-42 (Austria-Cruz, 2019). Additionally, Jones (2023) emphasizes the importance of collaboration between private security and law enforcement, concluding that public-private partnerships offer comprehensive solutions to modern law enforcement

challenges. These partnerships provide significant benefits in funding, personnel management, and addressing various security concerns.

On the other hand, Table 3 stressed that there is a major problem that the Appendix 111 PNP staff must overcome: the community's lack of support. It is evident from the respondents' significant agreement (mean score of 3.31), that this issue is a major barrier to efficiently settling particular cases. Thus, law enforcement officers may have trouble obtaining information, carrying out investigations, or gaining access to vital resources when communities do not cooperate or help when it comes to dealing with criminal situations.

This finding's analysis emphasizes how important community involvement is to law enforcement operations. In addition to impeding police officers' capacity to resolve specific cases, a community's lack of support can also be detrimental to larger efforts aimed at public safety and crime prevention. In the absence of proactive engagement and cooperation from community members, police enforcement organizations could encounter difficulties establishing credibility, acquiring information, and executing efficient deterrent strategies adapted toward communities.

Hence, it implied that law enforcement organizations should pay attention to resolving the absence of community support. It is important to support initiatives like outreach campaigns and community policing programs that try to strengthen the relationship between the police and the community. These efforts have the potential to enable communities to take an active role in crime prevention and resolution by promoting increased trust, communication, and cooperation between law enforcement and the community. Eventually, law enforcement organizations may increase public safety, strengthen communities, and increase their effectiveness by tackling the underlying causes of community disengagement and cultivating a sense of mutual trust and responsibility.

Moreover, Modise (2023) stresses the importance of police personnel establishing solid rapport with the communities they serve and being equipped to effectively navigate diverse racial and ethnic backgrounds. This collaboration is supported by most police officers who recognize its value in enhancing their effectiveness as social control agents. Similarly, Sharkey and Faber (2014) assert

that maintaining public safety and efficient policing relies on strong, trusting partnerships between police agencies and communities. Community assistance is essential for gathering information about crimes and addressing disorder and crime-related issues, while public trust in the police hinges on perceptions of legitimacy and adherence to procedural justice standards. Additionally, Etcuban et al. (2017) advocate for a shift in police organization towards stronger police-community relations, integrating traditional crime-fighting methods with problem-solving and prevention-focused approaches. This collaborative approach emphasizes joint efforts between law enforcement and communities to address crime and prevent future criminal activity, ultimately leading to safer neighborhoods.

As supported by one of the respondents, community support for the police contributes to overall community safety. This emphasized the importance of collaboration between law enforcement and residents in ensuring neighborhood security. Such cooperation can lead to more effective crime prevention and law enforcement efforts (Personal Communication, June 4, 2023).

On the other hand, it could be gleaned in table 3 that the police force faces several difficulties because of different sectors' lack of support. With a weighted mean score of 3.20, respondents mostly agree that the lack of help from other agencies is a disadvantage. This is also reflected in the case of barangay personnel's non-participation, where the mean score is 3.21. These results highlight how important community and interagency cooperation is to law enforcement initiatives. The lower scores of 2.95 and 2.96 for the absence of support from commercial organizations are also problem.

This implies that police performance is negatively impacted by inadequate external support, which makes their jobs more difficult and produces less than ideal results. The results highlight how important it is for the police and other agencies to work together to achieve successful law enforcement. The capacity of the police to carry out their

tasks effectively is jeopardized when agencies, Barangay employees, and private organizations fail to provide the necessary assistance. To maximize police effectiveness and enhance public safety results, these groups must have stronger collaboration and promote cooperation. Law enforcement agencies and outside partners can improve overall law enforcement performance and more effectively solve difficulties when they collaborate.

In alignment with these viewpoints, Velasco emphasized the indispensable role of community participation and support in effective law enforcement during the celebration of the 26th Police Community Relations Month at the Taguig City headquarters of the Philippine National Police-National Capital Region Police Office (Sarao, 2021). Additionally, Pajón and Walsh (2022) highlight the necessity for police officers to work in tandem with partner agencies in handling crimes, gathering intelligence, and conducting operations. Effective cooperation with partner agencies is vital for victim-centered and intelligence-led investigations. Furthermore, Szydłowski and Martyniak (2019) emphasize the need for ongoing frameworks to facilitate efficient collaboration between police officers and public institutions. Given the imperative nature of ensuring safety, effective partnerships and stable frameworks are crucial in law enforcement operations.

One respondent stressed the importance of collaboration between the Holy Spirit Police Station and the community. This emphasizes the essential role of cooperation in ensuring effective law enforcement and promoting community safety. Such collaboration enables the police to better understand local needs and concerns, fostering trust and mutual support. By working together, the police and the community can address crime and security challenges more effectively, leading to safer neighborhoods (Personal Communication, June 4, 2024).

➤ *Significant Difference in the Level of Agreement on the Severity of Factors affecting the Job Performance of the Respondents*

Table 5 Significant Difference in the Level of Agreement on the Severity of Factors affecting the Job Performance of the Respondents

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.220	2	.110	.400	.670
Within Groups	113.051	411	.275		
Total	113.271	413			

Legend:

P> .05 (not significant at 5% level)

P< .05 (significant at 5% level)

P.000- .01 (significant at 1% level)

Hypothesis Decision: If computed value (p-value) is greater than the critical value accept the null hypothesis. If computed value is less than or equal to the critical value reject the null hypothesis. Therefore, null hypothesis raised on this

study in terms Personal and Professional Factors, Work-related matter and Environmental Related matters was accepted, this implies that there is no significant difference on the assessment of respondents in terms of the three mentioned components which further implies that they have the same level of assessment concerning said variable.

In contrast, Crandall and Eshleman (2003) emphasize how personal and environmental factors shape individuals' expressions of prejudice, pointing to upbringing and societal norms as significant influences. Additionally, Thompson and Cavender (2020) stress the importance of collaboration

between law enforcement agencies and communities for effective policing, highlighting the teamwork involved in community-oriented policing efforts. Moreover, Tetrick and Peiró (2012) discuss how work-related and environmental factors affect employee well-being and performance, focusing on job demands and organizational support. Together, these studies suggest that while people may differ, certain universal factors like societal norms, teamwork in policing, and support from organizations can impact job performance assessments across different people. This highlights how personal, professional, and environmental factors all play a role in shaping how individuals perceive and evaluate job performance.

➤ *Framework:*

Framework can be generated that can contribute to the fund of knowledge. The proposed framework for improving job performance at the Holy Spirit Police Station is designed to address key personal, professional, work-related, and environmental factors that impact police officers. This comprehensive approach responds to challenges identified through research and aims to create an environment where officers can perform at their best.

Personal Factors: Personal issues, such as family problems, can significantly affect an officer's focus and performance. To mitigate these effects, the framework includes support mechanisms like counseling services and work-life balance programs. These initiatives help officers manage personal challenges more effectively, reducing stress and enhancing their professional performance and job satisfaction.

Professional Factors: Inadequate training can lead to reduced confidence and effectiveness among officers. The framework emphasizes the importance of continuous professional development through specialized training in leadership, crisis management, and technical skills. By offering regular workshops, seminars, and practical training, the framework ensures that officers are well-equipped to handle their responsibilities and adapt to evolving demands.

Work-Related Factors: The support from superiors is crucial for maintaining high morale and job satisfaction. The framework proposes regular feedback, mentorship programs, and clear communication channels to foster a supportive management style. This approach helps to build a positive work environment, motivating officers and enhancing their performance.

Environmental Factors: Poor working conditions, including inadequate facilities and equipment, can hinder effective policing. To address these issues, the framework suggests upgrading workstations, ensuring proper ventilation, and maintaining equipment. These improvements create a more functional and comfortable work environment, which supports better job performance.

This framework aligns with the research findings of Aliusman et al. (2018) and Mendoza et al. (2021). Aliusman's research highlights the positive impact of reassignment on motivation and job performance, while Mendoza's study identifies the significance of personality traits and professional factors in performance. By incorporating these insights, the framework aims to provide a comprehensive support system that addresses the multifaceted needs of police officers.

Rationale and Benefits: The goal of this framework is to enhance job performance and morale among police officers, which, in turn, improves public safety and community trust. By addressing personal issues, providing ongoing training, ensuring supervisory support, and improving working conditions, the framework creates an environment conducive to effective policing. This not only benefits individual officers but also strengthens the overall effectiveness of the police force and fosters a safer, more cohesive community.

In summary, the framework aims to support police officers by addressing critical factors impacting their performance. By focusing on personal support, professional development, managerial engagement, and improved work conditions, the framework seeks to foster a more capable and satisfied police workforce.

Fig 2 Framework for to enhance Service Delivery of the Philippine National Police.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusions

The findings from the study underscore the significant influence of both personal and professional factors on police officers' effectiveness at work. The overall well-being of officers emerges as a crucial determinant of their job performance. A positive work environment, characterized by strong organizational support, fosters a sense of commitment and belonging among officers. This environment encourages teamwork, mitigates stress, and enhances job satisfaction, all of which are integral to effective job performance.

The findings underscore that these work-related factors have a substantial impact on the efficacy and efficiency of police officers in carrying out their duties. Addressing these challenges is crucial for optimizing performance and ensuring effective service delivery. Improvements in working conditions, including better support from management, enhanced remuneration, more flexible scheduling, and safer working environments, are essential.

Moreover, revising inadequate leave policies, increasing incentives, providing adequate communication equipment, addressing vehicle shortages, and expanding health benefits are critical steps toward improving morale and performance. By tackling these issues comprehensively, the Holy Spirit Police Station can significantly enhance its officers' job satisfaction and overall effectiveness, ultimately leading to better service delivery and a more productive work environment.

To achieve optimal performance among police officers, it is essential for the organization to address and meet the comprehensive needs of its personnel. Ensuring that officers have access to adequate resources—including training, equipment, and support services—is crucial for enabling them to perform their duties effectively. Furthermore, addressing concerns related to compensation, work-life balance, and career advancement plays a significant role in enhancing officer satisfaction and motivation.

The findings also underscore the importance of fostering strong community relations and collaborating with other organizations. Building trust and cooperation with residents can significantly aid in crime prevention and enhance the effectiveness of crime-solving efforts. Additionally, partnerships with barangay authorities and other agencies can provide valuable resources and support, contributing to improved organizational efficiency and police effectiveness.

The researcher developed a framework to further enhance officers' job performance by addressing personal and professional challenges, improving work-related conditions, and fostering stronger collaboration with the community and other agencies. By implementing targeted interventions based on the study's findings, the action plan seeks to create a supportive environment conducive to effective policing.

B. Recommendations

To enhance the effectiveness and performance of police officers, the following recommendations are proposed based on the study's findings:

➤ *Promote Overall Well-Being:*

- **Support Services:** Implement comprehensive support services that address both personal and professional challenges. This could include counseling services, family support programs, and stress management resources.

- **Work-Life Balance:** Develop policies that help officers achieve a better work-life balance. Flexible scheduling and adequate leave policies can support officers in managing personal issues and reduce burnout.

➤ *Enhance Work Environment and Organizational Support:*

- **Positive Work Environment:** Foster a positive and inclusive work environment that encourages teamwork and reduces stress. Regular team-building activities and recognition programs can contribute to a supportive atmosphere.

- **Organizational Support:** Ensure that officers receive ample support from superiors, including regular feedback, mentorship, and opportunities for career development.

➤ *Career Advancement and Continuous Education:*

- **Training Programs:** Invest in continuous training and development programs that enhance officers' skills and knowledge. This includes providing access to advanced training in areas such as communication, leadership, and specialized police techniques.

- **Career Development:** Create clear pathways for career advancement within the organization. This can include promotional opportunities and professional growth initiatives that help officers build their careers.

➤ *Address Financial Stability:*

- **Compensation and Benefits:** Review and adjust compensation packages to ensure they are competitive and sufficient to meet the financial needs of officers. Consider providing additional financial support or incentives to alleviate financial burdens.

- **Financial Counseling:** Offer financial planning resources and counseling to help officers manage their finances effectively.

➤ *Improve Hiring Practices:*

- **Hiring Criteria:** Enhance hiring requirements to evaluate essential qualities such as communication skills, problem-solving abilities, and emotional intelligence. This will ensure that new recruits possess the necessary attributes for effective performance.

➤ *Focus on Personal Struggles:*

- **Personal Support:** Encourage officers to seek support for personal issues, including family or relationship problems. Providing access to confidential counseling and support services can help officers address these challenges and maintain focus on their duties.

To address the identified challenges and enhance the effectiveness and morale of police officers at the Holy Spirit Police Station, the following actions are recommended:

➤ *Improve Working Conditions:*

- **Renovate Work Areas:** Upgrade and maintain work areas to ensure they are comfortable and functional. This includes addressing issues such as poor ventilation and inadequate equipment.

- **Ensure Safe Working Conditions:** Implement safety measures to address any unsafe working conditions. Conduct regular safety audits and address potential hazards promptly.

➤ *Enhance Support and Supervision:*

- **Strengthen Support from Superiors:** Develop training programs for supervisors to improve their support and leadership skills. Encourage regular, constructive feedback and create avenues for officers to voice their concerns.

- **Increase Support Services:** Provide additional support services, such as mentoring programs and stress management resources, to help officers navigate their duties more effectively.

➤ *Revise Compensation and Benefits:*

- **Adjust Remuneration:** Review and adjust salary structures to ensure fair and competitive compensation. Consider introducing performance-based incentives and bonuses.

- **Expand Health Benefits:** Implement comprehensive health benefits, including mental health support, to address the well-being of officers more holistically.

➤ *Improve Leave Policies and Scheduling:*

- **Revise Leave Policies:** Develop and implement more flexible leave policies to better accommodate officers' personal needs and reduce burnout.

- **Enhance Scheduling Flexibility:** Introduce more flexible scheduling options to help officers manage their work-life balance and reduce stress.

➤ *Upgrade Equipment and Resources:*

- **Enhance Communication Equipment:** Invest in modern communication equipment to improve operational efficiency and effectiveness.
- **Address Vehicle Shortages:** Ensure that there is an adequate supply of vehicles to support officers in performing their duties efficiently.

➤ *Introduce Incentives and Recognition:*

- **Implement Incentive Programs:** Develop incentive programs that reward outstanding performance and contributions. Recognize achievements and provide opportunities for career advancement.
- **Foster a Positive Work Environment:** Promote a positive work culture through team-building activities and recognition programs to improve morale and job satisfaction.

To enhance the performance and effectiveness of police officers at the Holy Spirit Police Station, the following comprehensive recommendations are proposed:

➤ *Fulfill Personnel Needs:*

- **Provide Adequate Resources:** Ensure that officers have access to the necessary training, equipment, and support services to perform their duties effectively. This includes investing in modern technology, maintaining up-to-date equipment, and offering regular professional development opportunities.
- **Address Compensation and Benefits:** Review and adjust compensation packages to ensure they are competitive and meet the financial needs of officers. Implement a structured career advancement plan that includes clear pathways for promotion and development.

➤ *Enhance Work-Life Balance:*

- **Implement Flexible Scheduling:** Develop and offer flexible scheduling options to help officers balance their professional and personal lives. Consider options such as adjustable shifts and additional leave policies.
- **Promote Work-Life Balance Initiatives:** Introduce initiatives that support mental and physical well-being, including wellness programs and family support services.

➤ *Strengthen Community Relations:*

- **Engage with the Community:** Foster stronger relationships with the community through regular outreach, public engagement activities, and community policing initiatives. Building trust and cooperation with residents can enhance community safety and improve crime prevention efforts.

- **Collaborate with Local Authorities:** Work closely with barangay authorities and other local organizations to strengthen community ties and gain additional support and resources. Joint efforts can improve resource allocation and operational efficiency.

➤ *Facilitate Inter-Organizational Collaboration:*

- **Partner with Other Agencies:** Establish partnerships with other law enforcement agencies, non-governmental organizations, and community groups to enhance resource sharing and collaborative problem-solving. Such collaborations can provide valuable support and increase the effectiveness of police work.

➤ *Enhance Organizational Support:*

- **Improve Supervision and Support:** Train supervisors to provide better support and leadership. Ensure that officers receive regular feedback, mentorship, and opportunities to discuss their concerns and needs.
- **Invest in Continuous Education:** Support ongoing education and training for officers to keep them informed of the latest practices and innovations in law enforcement.

By implementing these recommendations, the Holy Spirit Police Station can significantly improve the performance and satisfaction of its officers. Addressing their needs, promoting a positive work environment, and enhancing community and inter-organizational relationships will lead to more effective policing, greater community trust, and a more engaged and motivated workforce.

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